

SYNTHESIS OF POLYNUCLEAR HYDROCARBONS WITH FUSED
cyclopentane RING. PART IV. HYDRINDENE DERIVATIVES
BY THE DIELS-ALDER REACTION

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The syntheses of several hydrindene derivatives, namely 4:7-dimethyl-5:6-diphenyl-, 4:7-diethyl-5:6-diphenyl-, 4-methyl-7-ethyl-5:6-diphenyl- and 4:5:6:7-tetraphenyl-hydrindenes have been carried out by the application of the Diels-Alder reaction. Other attempts in that direction have also been made.

There are comparatively few instances where the Diels-Alder reaction has been utilised for obtaining directly the indene ring system. $\alpha\beta$ -Unsaturated cyclic ketones, like 1-methyl-1-cyclopenten-5-one and 1-methyl-1-cyclopenten-4:5-dione, add with dienes to form indene ring system directly, though in the former case the tendency to form adducts is relatively small (Dane *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1937, 532, 29; 1939, 537, 246; 1938, 536, 196; Bockemüller, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1938, 51, 188). In a previous communication we had shown (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 897) that Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (II) could be used as an excellent dienophile in the Diels-Alder reaction. We have now utilised this dienophile to obtain the indene ring system directly. The dienophile (II) readily forms adducts with *cyclopentadienone* derivatives, forming indene ring systems with a carbonyl bridge. The removal of the carbonyl bridge on heating the adduct in a high boiling solvent, like tetralin, followed by decarboxylation, furnishes readily a substituted hydrindene.

4:7-Dimethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene (Va) has been synthesised starting from Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (II) and the dimer of 2:5-dimethyl-3:4-diphenylcyclopentadienone (Ia). The dienone dimer dissociates into the monomer in boiling xylene solution and forms the adduct 4:7:8:9-tetrahydro-4:7-dimethyl-5:6-diphenyl-4:7-endocarbonyl-hydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic anhydride (IIIa). This adduct readily loses the carbonyl bridge when heated at the temperature of boiling tetralin solution, forming 8:9-dihydro-4:7-dimethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic anhydride (IVa). The latter on distillation with soda-lime is decarboxylated and dehydrogenated, yielding 4:7-dimethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene (Va).

In a similar manner 4:7-diethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene (Vb) has been synthesised, starting from 2:5-diethyl-3:4-diphenylcyclopentadienone (Ib) and the anhydride (II). The adduct (IIIb) is readily formed when these two components are heated in xylene solution. The same adduct has also been obtained when $\alpha\beta$ -diethylanthroacetone-benzil, the carbimol, from which the dienone (Ib) is prepared, is taken in place of the dienone (Ib) and the reaction is conducted in acetic anhydride solution with the addition of a few drops of sulphuric acid. Under this condition the dienone (Ib) is formed and adds to the dienophile (II) present in the solution. The adduct (IIIb) has been converted into 4:7-diethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene (Vb) under the conditions used for converting

(IIIa) to (Va). 4-Methyl-7-ethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene (Vc) has also been synthesised starting from 2-methyl-5-ethyl-3:4-diphenylcyclopentadienone (Ic) and the anhydride (II).

During the synthesis of 4:5:6:7-tetraphenylhydrindene (Vd) it has been noted that the dienone, tetracyclone (Ib), and the anhydride (II) react in boiling xylene solution, affording directly the decarbonylated adduct (IVd). The product (IVd) when heated with soda-lime furnishes 4:5:6:7-tetraphenylhydrindene (Vd), identical with that obtained by Grumitto *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 604).

Anisylcyclohexene (Ie) and piperylcyclohexene (If) readily form adducts when heated respectively in boiling xylene solution with the anhydride (II). In the former case, the adduct (IIIe) retains the carbonyl bridge, whereas in the latter case the carbonyl bridge is lost during the reaction in boiling xylene, and the product isolated is (IVf). The adduct (IIIe) loses CO when heated in tetralin solution at 200°, affording (IVe). These two decarbonylated adducts could not be satisfactorily decarboxylated by heating with soda-lime, and the corresponding hydrindene derivatives have not been isolated.

- a: $R_2 = R_3 = \text{Ph}$; $R_1 = R_4 = \text{Me}$.
 b: $R_2 = R_3 = \text{Ph}$; $R_1 = R_4 = \text{Et}$.
 c: $R_2 = R_3 = \text{Ph}$; $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_4 = \text{Et}$.
 d: $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{Ph}$.
 e: $R_2 = R_3 = p\text{-MeO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$; $R_1 = R_4 = \text{Ph}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

4:7:8:9-Tetrahydro-4:7-dimethyl-5:6-diphenyl-4:7-endocarbonylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IIIa).—The dimer of, 2:5 dimethyl-3:4-diphenylcyclopentadienone, required for this experiment, was prepared by the dehydration of $\alpha\beta$ -dimethyl-anhydroacetone-benzil (Gray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 2134) and the latter was prepared from benzil and diethylketone (Japp and Meldrum, *ibid.*, 1901, 79, 1031). The dimer of 2:5-dimethyl-3:4-diphenylcyclopentadienone (Ia; 10 g.) and the anhydride of Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (II; 8 g.) were heated in xylene solution at 140°-145° (bath temperature) until the red colour of the solution almost had disappeared (4 hours). It was then allowed to stand overnight when the adduct separated. It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 217-18° (decomp.), yield 6.8 g. (Found: C, 78.3; H, 5.9; $C_{28}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 78.3; H, 5.5 per cent).

8:9-Dihydro-4:7-dimethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IVa).—The adduct (IIIa; 5 g.) was refluxed in tetralin (15 c.c.) solution until the evolution of CO had ceased (about 2 hours). Tetralin was removed by steam-distillation and the residue was crystallised from benzene-alcohol mixture, m.p. 205°, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 80.66; H, 6.2. $C_{28}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 81.08; H, 5.94 per cent).

4:7-Dimethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene (Va).—The bridgeless adduct (IV a; 5 g.) was mixed with soda-lime (8 g.) and heated in a Pyrex test tube under slightly reduced pressure when a liquid distillate (2 g.) was obtained. This slowly solidified. It was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 139°. (Found: C, 92.62; H, 7.8. $C_{22}H_{22}$ requires C, 92.61; H, 7.38 per cent).

4:7:8:9-Tetrahydro-4:7-diethyl-5:6-diphenyl-4:7-endocarbonylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IIIb).—Diethyldiphenylcyclopentadienone (Ib), required here, was prepared from $\alpha\beta$ -diethyl-anhydroacetone-benzil (Allen and Van Allan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 5166; Japp and Meldrum, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1040).

(A). Diethyldiphenylcyclopentadienone (Ib; 10 g.) and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (II; 8 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) were heated as described before. The adduct was washed with a little spirit and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 170° (decomp.), yield 6 g. (Found: C, 78.24; H, 6.3. $C_{28}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 78.8; H, 6.1 per cent).

(B). To a solution of $\alpha\beta$ -diethyl-anhydroacetone-benzil (5 g.) and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (3 g.) in acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) were added a few drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.). An exothermic reaction set in and the adduct separated after an hour. The reaction mixture was treated with water and the separated solid was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 170° (decomp.), yield 3.5 g. The mixed m.p. with a sample prepared by method (A) remained unaltered.

8:9-Dihydro-4:7-diethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IVb).—The adduct (IIIb; 5 g.) was decarbonylated as in the case of (IIIa), and the product was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 156°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 81.22; H, 6.9. $C_{27}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 81.4; H, 6.54 per cent).

4:7-Diethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene (Vb).—The bridgeless adduct (IVb; 5 g.) was heated with soda-lime (8 g.), as described before, when a liquid distillate was obtained. This was triturated with a little alcohol when it solidified. The hydrocarbon was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 128°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 91.79; H, 8.25. $C_{28}H_{30}$ requires C, 92.02; H, 7.97 per cent).

2-Methyl-5-ethyl-3:4-diphenylcyclopentadienone (Ic).—The dienone was prepared according to the general procedure outlined by Allen and Van Allan (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of cyclopentadienones. Benzil (42 g.) and *n*-propylethyl ketone (40 g.) were added to 500 c.c. of 0.5 % absolute alcoholic KOH solution, shaken and allowed to stand for 4 days. It was diluted with water, the separated oil extracted with benzene, dried and the solvent removed. The residual oil (35 g.) was mixed with acetic anhydride (60 c.c.) and a few drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.). Much heat was evolved and the mixture was allowed to stand for 12 hours at the ordinary temperature. The separated solid was washed with spirit and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 140° (decomp.), shrinking earlier, yield 18 g. This was evidently obtained as the dissociating dimer (Allen and Van Allan, *loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 87.43; H, 6.79. $C_{20}H_{18}O$ requires C, 87.59; H, 6.56 per cent).

4:7:8:9-Tetrahydro-4-methyl-7-ethyl-5:6-diphenyl-4:7-endocarbonylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IIc).—2-Methyl-5-ethyl-3:4-diphenylcyclopentadienone (Ic; 8 g.) and the anhydride (II; 8 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) were heated as before and the separated adduct was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 250° (decomp.), yield 5 g. (Found: C, 78.5; H, 5.8. $C_{27}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 78.6; H, 5.8 per cent).

8:9-Dihydro-4-methyl-7-ethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IVc).—The adduct (IIc; 5 g.) was decarbonylated in tetralin solution and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 194°, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 81.61; H, 6.6. $C_{26}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 81.25; H, 6.25 per cent).

4-Methyl-7-ethyl-5:6-diphenylhydrindene (Vc).—The decarbonylated product (IVc; 5 g.) was heated with soda-lime (8 g.) as described before. A liquid distillate was obtained, which slowly solidified and was crystallised from alcohol in stout needles, m.p. 105°. (Found: C, 92.6; H, 7.44. $C_{24}H_{24}$ requires C, 92.31; H, 7.69 per cent).

8:9-Dihydro-4:5:6:7-tetraphenylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IVd).—Tetracyclone (Id; 10 g.) (Dilthey and Quint, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1930, 128, 139) and the anhydride (II; 6 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) were refluxed until the dark violet colour of the ketone almost had disappeared (about 3 hours). Carbon monoxide was evolved during the reaction. On standing the colorless adduct slowly separated out. This was collected, washed with a little benzene to remove unchanged ketone and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 263-64°, yield 8 g. (Found: C, 84.6; H, 5.21. $C_{32}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 85.0; H, 5.2 per cent).

4:5:6:7-Tetraphenylhydrindene (Vd).—The adduct (IVd; 5 g.) and soda-lime (8 g.) were heated as described before. A solid sublimate was obtained. It was crystallised from benzene-hexane mixture, m.p. 223°. (Grumitto *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 225°). (Found: C, 94.2; H, 6.6. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{26}$: C, 93.83; H, 6.16 per cent).

4:7:8:9-Tetrahydro-4:7-diphenyl-5:6-di-p-anisyl-4':7-endocarbonyl-hydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IIIe).—Anisylcyclone (10 g.) (Dilthey *et al.*, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1934, 141, 331) and the anhydride (II; 6 g.) in dry xylene (30 c.c.) were heated and worked up as described before. The separated adduct was washed with a little cold benzene to remove the traces of anisylcyclone and was crystallised from benzene in colorless cubes, m.p. 138-39° (decomp.). (Found: C, 78.7; H, 5.6. $C_{31}H_{28}O_2$ requires C, 78.3; H, 5.15 per cent).

8:9-Dihydro-4:7-diphenyl-5:6-di-p-anisylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IVe).—The adduct (IIIe; 4 g.) was decarbonylated in tetralin solution. The product was washed with a little cold benzene and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 202°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 79.91; H, 5.6. $C_{27}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 80.14; H, 5.4 per cent).

8:9-Dihydro-4:7-diphenyl-5:6-bis-dioxy-methylenephanylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IVf).—Piperylcyclone (If; 8 g.) (Arbuzov and Akhmed-Zade, *J. Gen. Chem.*, U.S.S.R. 1942, 12, 212) and the anhydride (II; 5 g.) in xylene (25 c.c.) were heated as before. Carbon monoxide was liberated during the reaction. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight when the adduct separated out. It was collected, washed with benzene to remove traces of piperylcyclone and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 262° (decomp.), yield 4 g. (Found: C, 75.7; H, 4.7. $C_{37}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 76.28; H, 4.46 per cent).

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